

Overview

- Issues:** Residual distortion occurs due to thermal shrinkage discrepancies during the layer-by-layer deposition process¹.
- Polymer extrusion-based AM:** more significant due to the material's large thermal expansion.

Fig.1: Warpage on AM part.

Fig.2: Residual Distortion Mechanism in AM.

Objective

- Optimize process parameters to reduce residual distortion through accurate and rapid prediction.
- Control parameter:** layer deposition time².

Fig.3: Rapid Prediction Model Development Steps.

Method

- Temperature and deformation history prediction: Sequentially coupled thermomechanical model³.
- Dimensions (L x H x W, mm): 400 x 50 x 10, single bead wall
- # of training data set: 58,835,000

Fig.4: Geometry of wall structure.

Fig.5: High fidelity 3D FEA model for Temp. & Disp. Prediction.

- Artificial neural network (ANN) design:
 - Activation function: ReLu, Optimizer: Adam, Loss function: MSE, Early stop: on

Fig.6: Architecture of ANN. (input: 7, output: 3)

- Training and test data set design

Fig.7: Data set for training and test.

Results

- Temperature and displacement prediction through sequentially coupled thermos mechanical model with layer time 120 seconds.

Fig.8: (left) temperature field and (right) deformation field from FEA.

- ANN predicts 3D deformation field in minimal error with the trained data set.

Fig.9: Comparison of predicted deformation field from FEA and ANN with layer time 120 seconds.

- ANN predicts 3D deformation field in 8.29% error with the trained data set.

Fig.10: Comparison of predicted deformation field from FEA and ANN with layer time 145 seconds.

Fig.11: Comparison of maximum deformation in stacking direction with (left) training data set and (right) un-trained data set.

Conclusions & Future work

- Residual distortion varies with different layer deposition times.
- ANN shows good agreement with the FEA results for the trained data.
- For untrained data, the prediction shows a maximum error of 8.29%.
- Further improvement of the prediction accuracy and validation with experimental data

References

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